

A Study on Customers Perception towards Life Insurance Corporation of India Special Reference to Dharmapuri District

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Introduction of the Study

Introduction

The word "perception" comes from the Latin words *Percipio*, *percipio* means "receiving collecting, action of taking possession, anxiety with the mind and senses". Perception is the process by which organisms interpret and organize sensation to produce a meaningful experience of the world. Perception on the other hand, better describe one's ultimate experience of the world and typically involves further processing of sensory input.

Thus, perception in humans describes the process where by sensory stimulation is translated into organized experience. That experience, or percept, is the joint product of the stimulus and the process itself. Relation found between various types of stimulation and their associated percepts suggest inferences that can be made about the properties of the perceptual process, theories of perceiving that can be developed on the basis of these inferences. Because the perceptual process is not itself public or directly observable the validity of perceptual theories can be checked only indirectly perception is the process of attaining awareness or understanding of sensory information.

What is Insurance?

Insurance is a tool by which fatalities of a small number are compensated out of funds (premium payments) collected from plenteous. Insurance is a safe guard against uncertain events that may occur in the future. It is an deal where the losses experienced by a few are extended over several who are exposed to similar risks. It is a protection against financial loss arising on the happening of an unexpected event. Insurance companies collect premium to provide security for the purpose. Loss is paid out of the premium collected from people and the insurance companies act as trustees to the amount

so collected. These companies have proposal forms which are filled to give details of insurance required. Depending upon the answer in the proposal from insurance companies assess the risk and decide on the premium. Insurance companies are risk bearers.

Characteristics of Insurance

- Sharing of risks
- Cooperative device
- Evaluation of risk
- Payment on happening of a special event
- The amount of payment depends on the nature of losses incurred.
- The success of insurance business depends on the large number of people insured against similar risk.
- Insurance is a plan, which spread the risk and losses of few people among a large number of people.
- The insurance is a plan in which the insured transfers his risk on the insurer.
- Insurance is a legal contract which is based upon certain principles of insurance which includes utmost good faith, insurable interest, contribution, indemnity, subrogation, etc.,

Function of Insurance

Primary Function

1. Provide protection: Insurance cannot check the happening of the risk, but can provide for the losses of risk.
2. Collective bearing of risk: Insurance is a device to share the financial losses of few among many other.
3. Assessment of risk: Insurance determines the portable volume of risk by evaluating various factors that give rise of risk.
4. Provide certainty: Insurance is a device, which helps to change from uncertainty to certainty.

Secondary Function

1. Prevention of losses: Insurance cautions businessman and individual to adopt suitable device to prevent unfortunate consequences of risk by observing safety instructions.
2. Small capital to cover large risks: Insurance relieves the businessman from security investment, by paying small amount of insurance against large risks and uncertainty.
3. Savings and investments: Insurance companies are business houses. The product they sell in financial protection. To succeed and survive, they must cover their cost, which include payments to cover the losses of policy holders, as well as sales and administrative expenses, taxes and dividends.

Sources of Income

Insurance companies have two sources of income are

1. Premiums and
2. Investment income

Premiums are collected on a regular basis and invested in government bonds, stocks, mutual funds, real estates and other conventional avenues.

Investment income depends upon market conditions, interest rates, economy and varies from year to year. Because of the indecision associated with the investment income, insurance companies must generate enough income from premiums to cover the bulk of their expenses.

Advantages of Life Insurance

1. It is superior to an ordinary saving plan: Unlike other saving plans, it affords full protection against risk of death. In case of death, the full sum assured is made available under a life assurance policy; whereas under saving scheme the total accumulated saving alone will be available.
2. Easy settlement and protection against creditors: The life assured can name person(s) called nominee to whom the policy money would be payable in the event of his death. The proceeds of a life policy can be protected against the claim of the creditors of the life assured by effecting a valid assignment of the policy.
3. Ready marketability and suitability for quick borrowing: If the policyholder finds him unable to continue payment of premiums, he can surrender the policy for a cash sum. Alternatively, he can tide over a temporary difficulty by taking loan on the sole security of the policy without delay.
4. Tax relief: The Indian Income – Tax allows deduction of certain portion of the taxable income, which is diverted to payment of life insurance premiums from the total income tax liability. When this tax relief is taken into account, it will be found that the assured is in effect paying a lower premium for his insurance.

Various Types of Life Insurance Policies

1. Endowment policies: This type of policy covers risk for a specified period and at the end of the maturity sum assured is paid back to policyholder with the bonuses during the term of the policy.
2. Money back policies: This type of policy is for periodic payments of partial survival benefits during the term of the policy as long as the policy holder is alive.
3. Group insurance: This type of insurance offers life insurance protection under group policies to various groups such as employers- employees, professionals, co-operations etc., it also provides insurance coverage for people in certain approved occupation at the lowest possible premium cost.
4. Term life insurance policies: This type of insurance covers risk only during the selected term period. If the policy holder survives the term, risk cover comes to an end. These types of policies are for those people who are unable to pay larger premium required for endowment and whole life policies.
5. Joint life insurance policies: These policies are similar to endowment policies in maturity benefits and risk cover, but joint life policies cover two lives simultaneously such as married couples. Sum assured is payable on the first death and again on the death of survival during the term of the policy.
6. Pension plan: A pension plan or annuity is an investment over a certain number of years but does not provide any life insurance cover. It offers a guaranteed income either for a life or certain period.

Objective of LIC

1. Spread life insurance widely in particular to the rural areas to socially and economically backward class. This is done with a view to reach all the insurable persons in the country to provide them adequate financial cover against death at a reasonable cost.
2. To maximize mobilization of people's savings by making insurance linked savings adequately attractive.

3. Bearing in mind, the primary obligation to its policyholders, whose money hold in trust, the investible fund to be deployed to the best advantage of the investors as well as the national priorities and the obligations of attractive returns.
4. To conduct business with utmost economy and keeping in mind that the money belongs to the policyholders.
5. It acts as a trustee of the insured public in its individual and collective capacities.

Research methodology

Methodology is a systematic way of solving a problem it includes the research methods for solving a problem it includes the research methods for solving the problem.

Type of research

Descriptive cum Exploratory research

Data source

Primary and Secondary data

Data collection tools

Questionnaires

Sampling universe

Dharmapuri

Sample size

200

Sample Design

The target population of the study consists of various respondents of Dharmapuri. This survey will be done by collecting the data from the respondents.

Sample Size

After due consultation with the company supervisor as well as with the college guide, also keeping in mind the requirements of the company for the research, the sample size that was found to be appropriate for the study will be 150.

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique that adapted to conduct the survey was ‘Convenience Sampling’ and the area of the research was concentrated in the town of Dharmapuri. The survey was conducted by visiting different places like colleges, corporate offices, respondent’s home etc..

Data Source

The task of data collection begins after a research problem has been defined. In this study data will be collected through both primary and secondary data source.

Primary Data

A primary data is a data, which is collected for gathering information first time and to analyze the problem. In this study the primary data was collected among the consumers using questionnaire.

Secondary Data

Secondary data consist of information that already exists somewhere, having been collected for some other purpose. In this study secondary data was collected from company websites, magazines.

Review of Literature

Agarwala (1961)¹The LIC in India pointed out that in the developing countries, life insurance was an expanding phenomenon. Before the nationalization of the LIC, the life insurance market way narrow and highly imperfect, which was due to the under development of the country's national economy. But after nationalization, the LIC has made an excellent progress in the number of policies sold and the sum assured mobilized

Desai (1973)² in his study entitled, ' Life Insurance in India – its history and Dimensions of growth' stated that the origin and development of the life insurance in India over the years has wide spread mindedness in insurance and the significant sales through service initiatives, executive efficiency, economy and promptness and spreading the benefits of life insurance to vast section of the rural population and industrial workers throughout the country could achieve a formidable growth in LIC.

Chowdhury et al., (2004)⁷ Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) was the only company which dealt in Life Insurance and after opening of this sector to other private companies, all the world leaders of life insurance has started their operation in India. With their world market experience and network, these companies have offered many good schemes to lure all type of Indian consumers but unfortunately failed to get the major share of market.

Jain and Goyal (2006)¹⁰ (LIC) is adopting various strategies to develop customers' perception about the various products as well as involving in the fulfillment of various needs and requirements of the customers through their selection of different life insurance policies available in the market. Observing present scenario of the LIC customers' perception and their current transactional life insurance policies, in this study the investigation of customers' product awareness and transaction gap in Life Insurance Corporation of India.

Narendar and Sampath (2007)¹¹ The study tries to understand the awareness of the people towards the rights and duties towards life insurance products after the privatization of the insurance sector with special reference to Indian insurance sector. To actually understand this, a primary research was conducted to find out the level of awareness towards the rights and duties of the policy holders across demographic profiles and about the level of awareness towards life insurance policies prevailing in the Indian market. The study totally concentrates on the individual behavior, attitudes and also crating the awareness regarding their contribution on Indian insurance sector.

Table Respondents Opinion Regarding Insured

S.No	Respondents opinion	No. of respondents	Percentage %
1	Yes	135	68
2	No	65	32
Total		200	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation

Thus the above the table 4.8 shows that 68%of the respondents are insured in LIC and 32% of the respondents are not insured in LIC. Majority(68%) of the respondents are insured in LIC.

Table Response Opinion Regarding Towards Scheme of Insurance Policy

S. No	Scheme of insurance policy	No. of respondents	Percentages %
1	Whole life	51	25
2	Money back	74	37
3	Pension fund	63	32
4	others	12	6
Total		200	100

Source : Primary data

Interpretation

Thus the above table 4.13 shows that the respondents are prefer the insurance policy. 25% of the respondents are prefer whole life, 37% of the respondents are prefer money back, 32% of the respondents are prefer pension fund, 6% of the respondents are prefer others. Majority(37%) of the respondents are prefer money back scheme in insurance policy.

Table Respondents Opinion Regarging Satisfaction Level Towards Services Offered by LIC

S. No	Satisfaction level	Satisfaction level	Percentages %
1	Highly satisfied	Highly satisfied	16
2	Satisfied	Satisfied	42
3	Neutral	Neutral	36
4	Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	6
Total		200	Satisfaction level

Source : Primary data

Interpretation

The above the table 4.15 shows that the respondents satisfaction towards service offered by LIC. 16% of the respondents are highly satisfied to service offered by LIC, 42% of the respondents are satisfied to service offered by LIC, 36% of the respondents are neutral to service offered by LIC and 6% of the respondents are dissatisfied to service offered by LIC.

Majority(42%) of the respondents are satisfied to service offered by LIC.

Suggestions

1. To increase the level of insurance diffusion LIC may focus on bringing products that suit to the rural customers.
2. LIC should keep a check that its agents equally promote all its products.
3. The company if possible should invest in advertising, conduct road shows, and spend money on hoardings, so that it can better propagate awareness about its various lesser known products.

Conclusions

Insurance is a tool by which fatalities of a small number are compensated out of funds collected from plenteous. Insurance is a safeguard against uncertain events that may occur in the future. Company image is the highly important criteria that consumers consider before taking up a life insurance. This is mainly because people expect safety and secure for their money which they invest, followed by the factor Premium which we pay to the insurer and then Bonus, interest paid and good service provided by the company.

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